

Comparison of Outcome of Traumatic Brain Injury with Initial GCS at the Time of admission: A Prospective, Analytical StudyHarendra Kumar¹, Raj Kishore², Anshu Atreya³¹Junior Resident, Department of Surgery, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Junior Resident, Department of Surgery, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Senior Resident, Department of Surgery, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, with results depending on severity, demography, and clinical presentation. Commonly used to assess consciousness levels in TBI patients, the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) may predict prognosis.**Objective:** This study aims to evaluate the correlation between initial GCS scores at admission and patient outcomes, including mortality, neurological recovery, and hospital stay duration, in a cohort of TBI patients.**Methodology:** A prospective, analytical study of 160 traumatic brain injury patients was conducted at Patna Medical College & Hospital from November 2019 to October 2020. Initial GCS scores allocated patients to severe (GCS 3-8), moderate (GCS 9-12), and mild (GCS 13-15) TBI groups. Initial GCS mortality, neurological progress at discharge, and hospital stay were studied.**Results:** Severe TBI (GCS 3-8) had the highest mortality rate (41.7%) and poorest recovery outcomes, while mild TBI (GCS 13-15) had the highest recovery rate (83.3%) and lowest mortality (3.3%). Low initial GCS scores meant longer hospital stays. Early GCS scores are strongly correlated with patient prognosis.**Conclusion:** Lower initial GCS scores at admission predict increased mortality, poorer neurological outcomes, and longer hospital stays in TBI patients. This emphasizes GCS's reliability in early TBI assessment and prognostic planning.**Keywords:** Traumatic Brain Injury, Glasgow Coma Scale, Mortality, Neurological Outcome.

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Introduction

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) represents a major contributor to global mortality and disability, frequently leading to profound neurological and functional deficits necessitating extended care [1]. Traumatic brain injury (TBI) results from an external force, including a blow to the head or rapid acceleration-deceleration, that disrupts normal brain function. The severity of traumatic brain injury (TBI) varies from mild to severe, with outcomes differing significantly due to factors such as the mechanism of injury, patient age, time to medical intervention, and initial clinical presentation [2,3]. The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) serves as a prevalent clinical instrument for evaluating consciousness levels in individuals with traumatic brain injury (TBI). The system offers a standardized method for assessing eye, verbal, and motor responses, with score spanning from 3 (deeply unconscious) to 15 (fully alert) [4]. Initial GCS score correlate with injury severity and outcomes, whereas lower score is typically linked to increased risks of morbidity and mortality. Consequently, GCS functions as an essential predictor in trauma care,

aiding in the formulation of initial treatment strategies and the evaluation of prognosis [5,6].

The significance of GCS in TBI management is well acknowledged; however, the correlation between initial GCS score and long-term outcomes continues to be a subject of active investigation [7]. Numerous studies indicate a correlation between initial GCS score and survival rates, functional recovery, and neuropsychological outcomes; nonetheless, inconsistencies in results underscore the necessity for additional research [8].

This study analyses and compares outcomes of traumatic brain injury based on initial GCS score at admission, assessing its predictive value for patient recovery and survival. This analytical study aims to enhance the understanding of how initial GCS can inform prognosis and treatment strategies in TBI patients.

Methodology**Study Design:** This prospective, analytical study examines the connection between initial Glasgow

Coma Scale (GCS) scores upon admission and outcomes in TBI patients. The methodology permits systematic monitoring and investigation of initial GCS score effects on TBI prognosis.

Study Population: The study included a total of 160 patients diagnosed with traumatic brain injury who were admitted to Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, between November 2019 and October 2020.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 years and above.
2. Patients with confirmed traumatic brain injury on clinical and radiological examination.
3. Patients for whom GCS scoring was documented upon admission.
4. Patients admitted within 24 hours of the injury.
5. Cases of Traumatic Brain Injury admitted through emergency

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients younger than 18 years.
2. Patients with non-traumatic brain injuries (e.g., stroke, brain tumours).
3. Patients with incomplete medical records or missing GCS documentation at admission.
4. Patients who presented more than 24 hours post-injury.

Data Collection

Data was collected prospectively for each patient upon admission. Information collected included:

- Demographic details (age, gender)
- Mechanism of injury (e.g., road traffic accidents, falls, assaults)
- Initial GCS score at admission
- Radiological findings (CT/MRI of the brain)
- Treatment interventions (surgical or conservative)
- Duration of hospital stay

- Complications during hospitalization (e.g., infection, seizures)
- Discharge outcomes (survival, neurological status)

Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) Assessment

The initial GCS score for each patient was documented at the time of admission. Patients were classified based on their GCS scores into three groups:

1. Severe TBI: GCS 3-8
2. Moderate TBI: GCS 9-12
3. Mild TBI: GCS 13-15

Outcome Measures

The primary outcomes assessed included:

- Mortality rate
- Neurological recovery at discharge (categorized as good recovery, moderate disability, severe disability, or vegetative state)
- Length of hospital stay

Data Analysis: Statistical software was used to determine the relationship between initial GCS score and patient outcomes. The outcomes of severe, moderate, and mild GCS groups were compared using suitable statistical procedures (chi-square test for categorical data, ANOVA for continuous data). A p-value < 0.05 indicated significance.

Results

This research examined 160 patients with traumatic brain injury (TBI) who were admitted to Patna Medical College & Hospital from November 2019 to October 2020. Patients were classified according to their initial Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score upon admission into three categories: Severe TBI (GCS 3-8), Moderate TBI (GCS 9-12), and Mild TBI (GCS 13-15). The outcomes, encompassing mortality, neurological recovery, and duration of hospital stay, were analyzed for each group.

Demographic Distribution and Injury Characteristics

Variable	Severe TBI (GCS 3-8)	Moderate TBI (GCS 9-12)	Mild TBI (GCS 13-15)	Total
Number of Patients	60	40	60	160
Mean Age (years)	42 ± 15	38 ± 14	34 ± 12	38.1 ± 13
Gender (M/F)	45/15	30/10	50/10	125/35
Mechanism of Injury				
Road Traffic Accident	40	25	30	95
Fall	15	10	20	45
Assault	5	5	10	20

Out of 160 patients, 60 had severe TBI, 40 had moderate, and 60 had mild. Males predominated across all groups, and the severe TBI group had a

somewhat higher mean age. Road traffic accidents caused 59% of injuries, followed by falls (28%).

Outcome Measures Based on Initial GCS Scores

Outcome	Severe TBI (GCS 3-8)	Moderate TBI (GCS 9-12)	Mild TBI (GCS 13-15)	Total
Mortality Rate	25 (41.7%)	5 (12.5%)	2 (3.3%)	32 (20%)
Good Recovery	10 (16.7%)	20 (50%)	50 (83.3%)	80 (50%)
Moderate Disability	15 (25%)	10 (25%)	6 (10%)	31 (19.4%)
Severe Disability	10 (16.7%)	5 (12.5%)	2 (3.3%)	17 (10.6%)
Vegetative State	5 (8.3%)	-	-	5 (3.1%)

Death rates were highest in severe TBI (41.7%) and lowest in mild TBI (3.3%). Only 16.7% of severe TBI patients recovered well, while 83.3% of mild TBI patients did. The severe TBI group had more

severe impairments and vegetative states, demonstrating the importance of initial GCS on patient outcomes.

Length of Hospital Stay

GCS Group	Mean Hospital Stay (days)
Severe TBI (GCS 3-8)	18 ± 6
Moderate TBI (GCS 9-12)	12 ± 4
Mild TBI (GCS 13-15)	7 ± 3

The mean hospital stay for severe TBI patients was 18 days, compared to 12 days for moderate and 7 days for mild. Lower initial GCS score is connected with longer hospital stays to recover.

Discussion

This study evaluated the relationship between initial Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score at admission and outcomes in patients with traumatic brain injury (TBI). The results indicate a significant relationship between initial GCS scores and patient prognosis, encompassing mortality rate, recovery outcome, and duration of hospital stay [9]. The findings indicate that GCS is a valuable predictive instrument for evaluating TBI severity and estimating patient recovery potential. Patients exhibiting lower initial GCS score (3-8) demonstrated an increased mortality rate and inferior neurological outcomes relative to those with moderate (GCS 9-12) and mild TBI (GCS 13-15). In particular, 41.7% of patients with severe traumatic brain injury (TBI) died from their injuries, while only 3.3% of patients with mild TBI experienced the same outcome. A larger proportion of patients with mild traumatic brain injury (TBI) achieved good recovery (83.3%), whereas those with severe TBI exhibited significantly lower recovery rates (16.7%) and higher incidences of severe disability and vegetative states [10].

The results are in line with earlier studies that have demonstrated a negative correlation between outcomes and lower GCS scores. According to Myburgh et al. (2008) [11], GCS is a valid measure of the severity of the damage and the likelihood of recovery because lower GCS scores are significant predictors of death and impairment in TBI patients. Additionally, research by Lingsma et al. (2015) [12] showed that patients with initial GCS scores of 3–8 were more likely to experience adverse outcomes

compared to those with higher scores, which is consistent with our study findings regarding recovery and death. The predictive importance of GCS scores was examined in a study by Stocchetti et al. (2012) [13] in a cohort of 2,500 TBI patients. They discovered that the mortality rate for those with severe TBI was about 40%, which is quite similar to the 41.7% mortality rate in our study severe TBI group. The notion that higher GCS scores are linked to better results is supported by Stocchetti et al.'s observation that patients with moderate TBI had greater rates of functional recovery. In multicentre research to evaluate the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) predictive value, the CRASH trial collaborators (2008) found that a GCS score of less than 8 significantly increased the probability of death and severe disability. Our findings that those with moderate TBI (GCS 13-15) had the best prognoses were supported by the positive outcomes shown by patients with GCS scores between 13 and 15.

The findings of the current study align with those of Maas et al. (2010) [14], who performed a comprehensive analysis of predictive factors in TBI. The initial GCS, in conjunction with factors such as age and intracranial pathology, significantly impacts patient outcomes. Similar to our study, Maas et al. identified a correlation between lower GCS scores and extended hospital stays, increased mortality, and poorer neurological outcomes. The persistent correlation between GCS score and TBI outcomes in multiple studies underscores the significance of GCS as an essential element in the initial assessment of TBI. A low GCS score necessitates immediate and intensive care interventions due to the increased risk of mortality and long-term disability in these patients. Patients with mild TBI may benefit from a less aggressive management approach; however,

close monitoring for signs of deterioration remains essential.

Another outcome variable linked to GCS score was the duration of hospital stay. Hospital stays for patients with severe traumatic brain injury (TBI) were noticeably longer than those for patients with moderate or mild TBI. This implies that the initial Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score influences hospital care strategies, resource use, and survival and recovery outcomes. Early detection of patients who are likely to require extended hospital stays improves rehabilitation program planning and the distribution of healthcare resources [15]. Although this study has some limitations, it provides important information. The study sample is small and comes from only one center, which may limit how broadly the results may be applied. These results could be confirmed by bigger cohorts in future multicentre research. Additionally, this study did not look at characteristics that could affect TBI outcomes, such as age, comorbidities, and intracranial abnormalities. Including these variables could improve our knowledge of the determinants influencing TBI outcomes.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that initial GCS score are a dependable predictor of mortality, functional recovery, and length of hospital stay in patients with TBI. The results corroborate previous studies, reinforcing the significance of GCS in the initial evaluation of TBI severity and outcome forecasting. Integrating GCS into routine TBI management enhances prognosis assessments, optimises resource allocation, and facilitates more individualised care for patients with traumatic brain injuries.

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